

SEISMIC SLOPE STABILITY ANALYSIS OF EARTH DAM: SOME MODERN PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

The evolutions of practices of seismic slope stability analysis of earth embankment/dam are discussed in this paper. The basic concepts of various methods, salient features, advantages and limitations of each of them are elucidate. Methods for both stability analysis and deformation calculation are presented. Methods for calculation of deformation of post liquefaction stage are also briefed.

KEYWORDS

Earth dam, Seismic slope stability, limit equilibrium, Pseudo-static, Deformation, Liquefaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are numbers of natural calamities which cause damages and destruction of properties and injuries and death of lives. Amongst them, earthquake is considered to be the strongest forces in terms of severity of damages occurred to human civilization. Therefore it is very much important to understand the responses of structure against earthquake shaking.

In countries like India or many other countries in the world, where major part of the economy largely dependent on agriculture and consists of a numbers of rivers and canals, dams are often built to control flood and for irrigation purpose. These dams are often made by natural earth which is a softer material and thus it behaves like a flexible structure unlike concrete dam which behaves like nearly rigid structure. Earthen dams are especially important in terms of disaster prevention since they provide irrigation water and their damage can cause secondary destruction of nearby habitation.

Till recent time it is assumed that the earth dams have inherent reserve strength against earthquakes as most of the earth dams designed by static limit equilibrium method, withstand earthquake with slight or limited damage. But those dams may fail due to accumulation of damages resulted from the superposition of the dynamic forces from successive major earthquakes. Hence seismic slope stability analysis is becoming one of the most important criteria for safe design of earth dam so that adequate safety measures can be taken for better performance during earthquake.

This paper focuses the development of various methods of seismic slope stability analysis of earth dam considering the effect of a) dynamic stresses induced by earthquake shaking and b) the effect of those stresses on the strength.

2. SEISMIC SLOPE STABILITY ANALYSIS-HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT:

In the year 1936 Mononobe [1] perhaps the first to consider earth dam as deformable bodies and introduced the two-dimensional shear beam model. However after about twenty years this model got full attention and achieved the status of a complete engineering theory following the works by Hatanaka [2],[3] and then by Ambraseys [4],[5],[6]. For fundamental understanding of seismic

response of embankment, major contribution was made by Ambraseys. He assume that the soil is viscoelastic material and dam as one dimensional and use two dimensional shear beam model for analysis. Seeds and Martin [7] carried out similar analysis for variety of dam sizes and material properties and provided a comprehensive database for selecting appropriate values of seismic coefficient. They also pointed out the deficiencies of seismic coefficient method proposed by Hatanaka.

The advanced shear beam model was studied during 1960s and 1970s to interpret the results of full scale test, to conduct parameter studies and for better understanding of the problem and to develop seismic coefficients for design purpose.

Newmark [8] clarified many aspects of the problem of seismic stability of slopes. He said that even if the factor of safety in an equilibrium analysis incorporating seismic coefficient is less than unity, this need not imply that the dam is unstable instead dam underwent some local deformation as this situation would last for very short intervals (few seconds). He stressed that the deformation should be within tolerable limits. The limits of tolerable deformation should be based on characteristics of dam under study, judgement of experienced dam designers and the reliability of estimation of deformation.

In 1960 an important development took place when finite element method was first introduced and subsequent wide-spread use of this method lead the rapid development of geotechnical earthquake engineering. Clough and Chopra [9] first used this FEM method to estimate the seismic displacement of embankment dam. The popularity of finite element method is mainly due to the following factors (a) its capacity of handling any numbers of zones with deferent materials, whereas shear beam model assumed that the elastic property of the dam materials could be represented by an average value; and (b) its capability of rationally reproducing the 2-D dynamic stress and displacement field during earthquake shaking, whereas the simplifying assumption of uniform horizontal shear stresses in shear-beam analysis seemed to violate the physical requirement of vanishing stresses on the two sloping faces of the dam.

Seismic slope stability analysis may be grossly divided into two categories on the basis of which effect on the given slope is predominant. The first category is *internal instability* where the shear strength of the soil remains relatively constant but slope deformations are occurred by dynamic earthquake stresses which goes above the strength of soil temporarily. The second category is *weakening instability* where the earthquake force weakens the soil sufficiently so that the dam structure cannot remain stable under earthquake induced stresses. Flow liquefaction and cyclic mobility are the most common causes of weakening instability.

2.1. PSEUDO-STATIC STABILITY ANALYSIS

In absence of knowledge of seismic responses against earthquake, the seismic stability of earth structure can be analyzed by Pseudo static approach in which the effect of an earthquake are represented by constant horizontal and vertical acceleration. In the most common form, pseudo static analysis represents the effect of earthquake shaking by pseudo static acceleration, that produce inertia forces F_h & F_v which act through the centroid of the failure mass as shown in fig

1. Then $F_h = \frac{ahW}{g} = k_h W$, $F_v = \frac{avW}{g} = k_v W$.

Fig1 Force acting on triangular wedge of soil above failure plane

Here a_h and a_v are the horizontal and vertical pseudo static acceleration, k_h and k_v are the horizontal and vertical pseudo static coefficients, W is the weight of the failure wedge. Resolving the forces on the potential failure mass in a given direction parallel to the failure surface,

$$\text{Factor of Safety} = \frac{\text{resisting force}}{\text{driving force}} = \frac{c l_{ab} + [(W - F_v) \cos \beta - F_h \sin \beta] \tan \phi}{(W - F_v) \sin \beta + F_h \cos \beta}$$

where c and ϕ are Mohr-Coulomb strength parameter and l_{ab} is the length of the failure plane. Since the vertical pseudo static force has less influence on the factor of safety, the effect of vertical acceleration are frequently neglected in pseudo static analysis.

Horizontal seismic coefficient can be estimated by any of the several methodologies developed by Bishop [10], Morgenstern and Price [11], Janbu [12] and Spencer [13]. Seed [14] listed pseudo static design criteria of 14 dams in 10 seismically active countries. But there are no hard and fast rules for selection of pseudo static coefficients for design. It should be based on actual anticipated level of acceleration of failure mass and that it should correspond to some fraction (0.1 to 0.25 - varies countries to countries) of the anticipated peak acceleration. Although engineering judgment is required for all the cases.

Though the pseudo static analysis is a very straight forward and relatively simple method, this approach has some serious drawbacks which have been thoroughly discussed by Seed [15]. The major drawbacks are listed below:

1) The method of analysis is based on the erroneous assumption that the dam is absolutely rigid body fixed on its foundation and experiencing a uniform acceleration equal to the underlain ground acceleration.

2) The horizontal inertia forces do not act permanently and in one direction but rather fluctuate rapidly in both magnitude and direction. Thus even if the factor of safety drops momentarily below one, the slope would not experience gross instability but undergoes some permanent deformation.

3) This approach considers only slope instability as the only potential mode of failure. But in practice there are several other types of seismic damages which may occur in the earthen dam. These damages may be

- (a) Liquefaction flow failure due to excess pore water pressure in contractive saturated non-cohesive zone.
- (b) Longitudinal cracks occurring near the crest due to shear sliding deformations and large tensile strains during lateral oscillation.
- (c) Differential crest settlements and loss of free board possibly resulting from lateral sliding deformations or soil densification.
- (d) Transverse cracks caused by tensile strains from longitudinal oscillations or by different lateral response near the abutments and near the central crest zone, and
- (e) Piping failure through cracks in cohesive soil zones.

2.2. DEFORMATION ANALYSIS

Some of the above mentioned deficiencies were largely overcome by 'sliding displacement' method originally proposed by Newmark [8]. He suggested that whenever the inertia force on a potential slide mass exceeds its yield resistance, sliding movements occur; when the inertia forces are reversed the movements stop and may even be reversed.

2.2.1. Analytical Methods:

In Newmark's analysis, deformation of a dam is modeled as the displacement of a rigid block sliding on an assumed failure surface under the ground motions at the sites. Various potential sliding surface in the embankment were analysed statically to find the inertia force $F_1 = (W/g)a_y$ required to cause failure (fig 2). The average yield acceleration a_y is then deduced from this force. The sliding block is assumed to have same acceleration time history as the ground (assume the dam as rigid). The yield acceleration is deducted from the acceleration time history and the net acceleration is available to generate permanent displacement which is evaluated by simply double integration. The analysis was done on the analogous model of a sliding block resting on an inclined plane with only one directional (horizontal) motion allowed.

Fig 2 Elements of Newmark's deformation analysis

Makdisi and Seed [16] modified the Newmark's method by taking into account the flexibility of the dam. The average acceleration time record of the sliding block was computed by the method proposed by Chopra (QUAD-4 analysis) [9]. The dynamic response of the dam is accounted for by an acceleration ratio that varies with the depth of the potential failure surface relative to the height of the embankment. By interpreting the results of EQL finite element analyses of several dams, they related the average peak acceleration ratio (K_y/K_{max}) of the sliding mass, with normalized peak displacement ($u/K_{max}gT_0$) for several magnitudes of earthquake. Knowing the fundamental period of vibration of dam and the yield acceleration ($K_y g$) of the slope, simple charts given by Makdisi and Seed (fig 3) can be used to estimate earthquake induced displacements.

The displacement analyses can provide approximate idea of probable deformation of cohesionless soil under conditions in which appreciable change in pore pressure does not occur during earthquake motion. Thus in case where the shell of a dam consists of granular material either unsaturated or freely draining, these procedures should give realistic value of displacement. However, in case of saturated non-cohesive material or cohesive soils in which pore pressure build-up may occur during an earthquake no suitable analytical method is available and an estimate of displacement can only be made based on laboratory test.

Fig 3 Simplified estimation of normalized displacements by Makdisi–Seed’s procedure.

To evaluate the seismic stability of such embankment Seed *et al.*[17] developed an analysis procedure called “Strain Potential Approach” which involves the following essential steps :

- (a) estimate the initial static stresses in the embankment, by means of finite element analysis;
- (b) determine the dynamic soil properties such as shear modulus, passion ratio, and damping as functions of strain level;
- (c) compute the stresses induced in the embankment by the design ground excitation, using plain-strain finite element analysis and the dynamic soil characteristics as determined in step b;
- (d) determine the generation of pore pressures and the subsequent reduction of it strength and development of potential strains by performing laboratory testing on representative soil samples subjecting to the combined effect of the initial static and the induced cyclic stresses; and
- (e) perform slope stability analysis and semi-empirically convert the strain potentials to a sets of compatible deformations.

The stability and performance of the dam are judged from the results of these stability analyses and/or the size and distribution of the compatible deformations within the dam.

Another method for estimating permanent slope displacement was developed by Lee [18] and Serff *et al.*[19] which is called as “stiffness reduction approach”. Stiffness of the soil is used to reduce according to the strain potential of the soil. Earthquake induced slope displacements are then estimated as the difference between the nodal point displacements from two finite element analysis; one using the initial shear modouli and other using the reduced shear moduli. This technique can estimate horizontal as well as vertical displacement unlike strain potential approach where only horizontal displacement can be determined.

2.2.2. Some Empirical methods:

Empirical methods are based on the observed or computed performance of existing dams and correlate crest settlement with peak ground motion parameter.

Jansen [20] developed a empirical relationship between earthquake magnitude M , the maximum crest acceleration K_m , the yield acceleration K_y , and the total crest settlement U as;

$$U = [48.26(M/10)^8(K_m - K_y)] / K_y$$

The value of amplification factor at the crest K_m , in the above equation can be obtained from a relation with PGA given by him.

Swaigood [21] developed a methodology to estimate seismic crest settlements of data collected from the seismic performance review of about 60 existing dams. He related the crest settlement

(CS), expressed in percent of combined dam and alluvium thickness, to a seismic energy factor (SEF) and three constants based on types of dam construction (K_{typ}), dam height (K_{dh}) and alluvial thickness (K_{at}) as follows;

$$CS = SEF \times K_{typ} \times K_{dh} \times K_{at}$$

The seismic energy factor (SEF) in the above equation is dependent on the possible magnitude of earthquake (M) and peak ground acceleration (PGA) at the dam site and is expressed as ;

$$SEF = e^{(0.7168M+6.505PGA-9.098)}$$

K_{typ} depends on the type of dam construction. K_{typ} is 1.87 for earth core rockfill dams and concrete faced rockfill dams, 1.363 for earthfill dam and 4.620 for hydraulic fill dams.

The expression for K_{at} and K_{dh} are as follows;

$$K_{at} = 0.851 \times e^{(0.00368At)} \quad \text{and} \quad K_{dh} = 9.134 \times H^{-0.437}$$

Where At is the alluvial thickness present beneath the dam and H is the height of the dam. The above factor indicates that the higher dams settle less than smaller dams.

Bureau [22] presented a relationship as shown in fig 4, which relates relative crest settlement(%) to the Earthquake Severity Index (ESI). He gives an expression of ESI as follows;

$$ESI = PGA \times (M - 4.5)^3$$

Fig 4 Relative settlement (%) Vs. ESI (Bureau 1997)

Other simplified approaches for estimating dam deformations can be found in the literature given by Romo and Resendiz [23]. If liquefaction is of concern to the dam or its foundation, the simplified procedure proposed by Seed and Idriss [24] can be implemented for dams with flat slopes. A better approach is to assess the liquefaction potential from corrected field penetration data(Seed *et al.* [25]; Seed [26]).

Nonlinear(NL) Analysis Approach : With the advancement of computational technique by the development of computer it is now possible to compute the permanent deformation by finite element(both 2D and 3D) and finite difference analysis using nonlinear inelastic soil model using both cyclic stress strain models and advance constitutive models. These methods apply when loss of strength, large deformations, or liquefaction are a concern for the embankment or its foundation. A significant advantage of NL analysis is that the same numerical model can be used for both static and dynamic condition. But the accuracy of nonlinear finite element analysis largely depends on the accuracy of the stress strain or constitutive model on which they are based.

2.3. EVALUATION OF POST LIQUEFACTION BEHAVIOR

Liquefaction is a phenomenon wherein a mass of soil loses a large percentage of its shear resistance when subjected to monotonic, cyclic or shock loading and flows in a manner resembling a liquid until the shear stress acting on the soil mass are as low as the reduced shear resistance. Liquefaction is most commonly observed in shallow, loose, saturated deposits of cohesionless soils subjected to strong ground motions in large magnitude earthquakes. Unsaturated soils are not subjected to liquefaction because volume compression does not generate excess pore pressure.

Flow liquefaction can occur when the static shear stresses in a liquefiable soil deposit is greater than the steady-state (residual) strength of the soil. It can produce devastating flow slide failures during and after an earthquake shaking. Flow liquefaction can occur only in loose soil.

Cyclic mobility can occur when the static stress is less than the steady-state(residual) shear strength and the cyclic shear stress is large enough that the steady state strength is exceeded momentarily. Deformation produced by cyclic mobility failure develops incrementally but become substantial at the end of a strong and /or long duration earthquake. Cyclic mobility can occur in both loose and dense soils but deformation decreases markedly with increased density.

Flow failure instability is usually estimated by limit equilibrium analysis. Residual strengths are applied to those portions of the failure surface that pass through liquefied soil. A factor of safety less than one suggest that flow failure is likely. Simple limit equilibrium analysis combined with constant volume constraints can be used to estimate the distance over which the material travel in flow failure (Lucia et al.[27]). Fluid mechanics models have also been used to estimate the flow slide behavior (Johnson [28]; Iverson and Denlinger [29]). Nonlinear dynamic analyses that allow weakening of liquefied elements and large strain have also developed using finite element program, for example TARA-3FL developed by Finn and Yogendrakumar [30]. This program periodically updates the finite element mesh at each step to calculate the large deformation. Each calculation of incremental deformation is based on the current shape of the dam not the initial shape as in conventional finite element analysis. The post liquefaction deformed shape of Sardis Dam using TARA-3FL finite element program is shown in fig 5.

Fig 5 Deformed cross-section of Sardis Dam

Deformation failures generally involves small deformations than flow failure. The effect of deformation failures are usually expressed in terms of slope deformation. Lateral spreading is the most common type of deformation failure. A number of researchers have developed the methods of calculation of deformation failure. Some of the approaches are purely empirical (Hamada *et al.* [31], Youd and Perkins [32], Bartlett and Youd [33]). Byrne [34] developed equation for calculation of deformation based on work energy principal. Bazier *et al.* [35] used sliding block analysis for calculation of permanent lateral displacement.

All the above methods produce displacements are approximate only. The applicability of each method to a particular site depends on the similarity between the condition at that site and those corresponding to the databases from which the method was developed.

3. CONCLUSION

The major geotechnical problem facing dam experts in the seismic region is evaluation of safety of newly proposed dams as well as existing dams. To make a realistic prediction of the response of the earth/embankment dam to a particular earthquake shaking, the following factors must be considered carefully

- a) Non-linear inelastic behavior of soil
- b) Dependence of soil stiffness on confining pressure
- c) Narrow canyon geometry
- d) Dam alluvium interaction.

For a particular dam one or more factors may have major influence on the responses of the dam. Accordingly the appropriate methods of analysis should be chosen. If the dam is not strongly nonlinear and the pore pressure development is not significant, the performance of the dam may be determined by equivalent linear analysis. Otherwise more comprehensive method like nonlinear finite element method of analysis would be adopted when appropriate especially for evaluating of large deformation resulting from strong shaking with or without the presence of liquefaction. Therefore a well designed dam is well within the capabilities of the profession of dam engineering. The assessment of existing dam which may have potentially liquefiable zone can also be done conveniently and accordingly the remediation requirements are suggested.

The technique to simulate the response of the earth dam against earthquake by mathematical modeling or by computer based FDM or FEM are not simple. But by the advancement of computer, it is now possible to create models of earth dam for safety analysis close to the reality. But still there are lots of uncertainties present in the available procedure. Therefore the future challenges of the researchers are to reduce these uncertainties and ensure the safety of the dams for longer periods (i.e. 1000 years) as per new environmental standards.

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